

BODY MASS INDEX AS A PREDICTOR OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EPIDURAL FIBROSIS.

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Introduction. One of the main reasons for the development of “failed back surgery syndrome” is considered to be the formation of a connective tissue scar in the epidural space in patients after discectomy. Quite a large number of methods for pre- or intraoperative prevention of this process have been proposed, but the factors contributing to its development in the postoperative period have been little studied.

Material and research methods. We studied the data of 68 patients who underwent surgery for removal of a herniated intervertebral disc. All patients, to one degree or another, developed epidural fibrosis. Having studied a large number of preoperative indicators, we identified a number of factors that, to varying degrees, influenced or correlated with the development of a cicatricial adhesive process in the epidural space in these patients.

Research results. Factors influencing the further development of epidural fibrosis in the 68 patients we studied were: excess body weight, the condition of the ligamentum flavum, the degree of spinal canal stenosis, the degree of intervertebral disc degeneration, leukocytosis, and the amount of fibrinogen in the blood. A directly proportional relationship was identified between the above indicators and the rate and severity of development of epidural fibrosis. The clearest connection was determined with an increase in body mass index, that is, grade 3 obesity gave an almost guaranteed 31.4% risk of developing scar-adhesive complications in the epidural space after surgery.

Conclusion. If the patient is overweight, it is necessary to take into account that this indicator is a predictor of the development of epidural fibrosis and this category of patients should be fully carried out a set of measures aimed at preventing epidural fibrosis

